

Running and modifying the model

Installing the software

N.B. In order to carry out this activity and all the ones that follow in the course, you need a computer that has **Windows 10 Operating System.**

The OSeMOSYS UI (User Interface) is needed for viewing, using, running and modifying the Namibia CLEWs model. Follow these steps to install the interface:

To install the user interface:

1. Download the .exe installation file from [here](#).
2. Move the .exe file from your download folder to a folder where you have administrator privileges. This may be for instance inside the folder: **users / *name_of_the_user*** or any other folder you prefer.
3. Click on osemosys.3.1.0.exe and install the UI. A window will open showing that the installation is ongoing. Please leave it open. The process may take a few minutes. When the installation is completed, the window will close automatically and the user interface should open automatically.
4. Once the installation has been completed the interface should open automatically. If the window is blank, then close it and open the interface manually: An icon for the interface should have appeared on your desktop. Double-click on it.
5. If after these steps the interface still does not open, then open the installation folder (i.e., C:\Users\your_user\AppData\Local\osemosys) and find the file 'osemosys.exe'. Right-click on it and '**Run as administrator**'.
6. You will see the UI in a new window as in the figure below.

If you want to reopen the user interface any other moment in the future, you should be able to find it in the Windows Start bar as an app, or you should have a shortcut on the Desktop.

Uploading the model on your computer

Once you have installed the software (OSeMOSYS UI), you are ready to upload on it the chosen CLEWs model.

Follow these steps to upload the model:

1. Download the model from wherever it is shared, onto your desktop (it will be downloaded as a zipped folder), and place it in a folder of your choice. **Do not unzip it and do not change the name of the file**, otherwise you will not manage to upload it on your computer.
2. Open the OSeMOSYS UI. In the Home screen, you will see an icon to 'Restore model' (see figure below). Click on it.

3. A window will appear, asking to 'Drop Case to restore (or click)', as in figure below. Click on it, navigate to the folder where you put the downloaded model, select it with one click and click 'open'.

4. The model will be loaded onto your interface and appear in the Home screen as in the figure below. Note that the model will have a different name from the one displayed in the figure (which is just an example).

Running the CLEWs model

Once the model is correctly uploaded on the interface, you are ready to run it on your computer. Take the following steps:

1. After having selected the model in the Home screen of the interface (just click on its name to select it), click **Run** in the list on the left of the Window.

- This takes you to the creation of a new 'Case'. A 'Case' is nothing but one specific run of your model, for example to check how the results change when you change some parameters. You can create many cases, each one with some variations of some parameters of interest, and then compare them.

Write the name of the 'Case name' (e.g. 'REF', which stands for reference scenario), and, if you want, a 'Case description.'

- After that, click on 'Scenario order'.
- This takes you to a window where you are asked to select or deselect some items. These items are specific sets of assumptions, previously created, which you can include or not include in the model, and you can combine in different ways. Each set of assumptions is called a 'scenario'. That is why the button says 'scenario order'.

- We now run the reference scenario. For running the reference scenario you need to deselect all the sets of assumptions that have been created. This will make so that only the base

dataset of the model is used in this case, with no additional changes. After deselecting the scenarios like in the figure, click on Save.

6. Now you may click on 'Create case.'

7. You will see the newly created case appear on the right. Now click Generate Data File.

- This step generates a text file (which appears on the right and you can download, if you want – but not needed) which compiles all the inputs of the model in a simple format. This step is needed by the solver, so that it may read all the input data and run the optimization. Now click **'Run the model.'**

- If the run completes successfully, you will see a green message appear at the top. You will also see several tabs on the right panel, in which you can check the solver log (which contains all information about the optimization and any potential error messages) and all the model results as a 'CSV' files.

Visualizing the results

The OSeMOSYS UI has embedded a tool for the visualization of results.

OSeMOSYS delivers results for many variables. It is lengthy to look at all, and many are not essential in most cases. We will guide you on how to view results for one of the most important variables: ‘Production by Technology Annual’. This variable shows the outputs of the various objects in the model (e.g. electricity, if they are power plants, or crops, if they are agricultural land, etc.).

1. Select the variable from the drop down menu on the top-left.

- Now you will come to a screen where you can select the values to be shown and how to structure your graph. Note, this works exactly in the same way as pivot tables work in excel. The concept is the same. Select on the left panel the fields: Case, Year, Value, and Tech.

Choose fields to add to report:

- Case
- Comm
- Comm Desc
- Year
- Value
- Unit
- Tech
- Tech Group
- Tech Desc
- Tech Group Desc

- Drag the fields in the different areas for visualization, for example:

Drag fields between areas below:

Filters Case	Columns Tech
Rows Year	Values Value (Sum)

Defer Updates Update

4. In each area, you can filter out the items of your choice. For example, we want to visualize the technologies generating electricity. Right-click on the area 'Columns', where to drag the field called 'Tech,' and select 'Field Settings.' In Filter, you can Edit the technologies you want to visualize, in this case, all the power technologies (PWR---).

The screenshot shows the OSeMOSYS ver.4.2 interface. On the left is a dark sidebar with buttons for 'View data', 'Run', and 'Results'. The main area is divided into 'MODELS' and 'Columns'. The 'MODELS' section has a 'Select model' dropdown. Below it is a list of fields with checkboxes: 'Comm Desc', 'Year', 'Value', 'Unit', 'Tech', 'Tech Group', 'Tech Desc', and 'Tech Group Desc'. The 'Tech' field is checked and has a dropdown arrow. Below this is a section titled 'Drag fields between areas below:' with 'Filters' and 'Columns' sections. The 'Columns' section has a 'Tech' field selected, and a context menu is open over it with options: 'Move Up', 'Move Down', 'Move to Beginning', 'Move to End', 'Move to Report Filter', 'Move to Row Labels', 'Move to Column Labels', 'Move to Values', 'Remove Field', and 'Field Settings...'. At the bottom, a table shows 'Year' and 'PWRCOA' columns, with '2020' in the first row.

Year	PWRCOA
2020	

Field settings: Tech

Header:

Summary: ▼

Show As: ▼

Weigh by: ▼

Sort: ▼

Filter: **Edit...** Clear

Format: [Filter by Condition](#) | [Filter by Value](#)

Sample:

Select All

- DEMPWRLNG
- DEMPWRSURWAT
- PWRBIO001
- PWRCOA001
- PWRCOA002

OK Cancel

OK

MPELC004 R001 IMPKER00

5. On the top panel, select a chart, for example, 'Column', and for better visualization, 'Stacked.' You can see the figure of the parameter Accumulated new capacity.

- Other utilities of the UI for visualization. On the top right of the UI, you will see several tabs. Commonly, you can export the figure as a PNG file or as an Excel file. One of the most important tabs is called 'Create view.' After you customise your own graph to visualize specific results (like you did above), you can use this Tab to 'save' the settings, so that you may recreate the same graph just with one click and see new results when you re-run the model. In our example, if you made 'Create a view' for the Production by Technology Annual, you will be able to select that view for future runs of your model. If you run a new model with updated data, you will see a plot similar to the one you configured in the first place by selecting the view. However, if you need to check the production of tech you did not choose while creating a view, you will need to add it manually as you did in step 5

